

**O'ZGARMAS KOEFFITSIYENTLI INTEGRO-DIFFERENSIAL TENGLAMALAR
SISTEMASINI YECHISHNING DALAMBER USULI**

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada bir jinsli bo'lmagan chiziqli integro-differensial tenglamalar sistemasi uchun Koshi masalasi yechimi Dalamber usulidan foydalanib aniqlangan.

Quyidagi

$$(1) \quad \begin{cases} D_{mt}^\alpha x(t) = aI_{mt}^\gamma x(t) + bI_{mt}^\gamma y(t) + f_1(t), \\ D_{mt}^\alpha y(t) = cI_{mt}^\gamma x(t) + dI_{mt}^\gamma y(t) + f_2(t), \end{cases} \quad t > m$$

sistemaning

$$(2) \quad \lim_{t \rightarrow m} I_{mt}^{1-\alpha} x(t) = x_0, \lim_{t \rightarrow m} I_{mt}^{1-\alpha} y(t) = y_0$$

boshlang'ich shartlarni qanoatlantiruvchi yechimini topish masalasini qaraylik, bu yerda D_{mt}^α va I_{mt}^γ kasr tartibli Riman-Liuvill ma'nosidagi differensial va integral operatorlar bo'lib[1], quyidagicha aniqlanadi:

$$D_{mt}^\alpha z(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)} \frac{d}{dt} \int_m^t (t-s)^{-\alpha} z(s) ds,$$

$$I_{mt}^\gamma z(t) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(\gamma)} \int_m^t (t-s)^{\gamma-1} z(s) ds,$$

$\Gamma(z)$ - Eylerning gamma-funksiyasi[2], $\alpha, \gamma, a, b, c, d, x_0, y_0$ - berilgan haqiqiy sonlar bo'lib, $0 < \alpha < 1$, $\gamma > 0$; $f_1(t)$ va $f_2(t)$ berilgan funksiyalar, $x(t)$ va $y(t)$ lar esa noma'lum funksiyalar.

{(1),(2)} Koshi masalasining yechimini topish bilan shug'ullanamiz. Dastlab, (1) ning ikkinchi tenglamasini λ songa ko'paytirib so'ngra birinchi tenglamaga qo'shamiz. Natijada quyidagi tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$(3) \quad D_{mt}^\alpha [x(t) + \lambda y(t)] = (a + \lambda c) I_{mt}^\gamma x(t) + (b + \lambda d) I_{mt}^\gamma y(t) + f_1(t) + \lambda f_2(t).$$

(3) ni quyidagi ko'rinishda yozib olamiz:

$$(4) \quad D_{mt}^\alpha [x(t) + \lambda y(t)] = (a + \lambda c) \left[I_{mt}^\gamma x(t) + \frac{b + \lambda d}{a + \lambda c} I_{mt}^\gamma y(t) \right] + f_1(t) + \lambda f_2(t).$$

λ sonni shunday tanlaylikki, u ushbu $\frac{b + \lambda d}{a + \lambda c} = \lambda$ tenglamaning yechimi bo'lsin.

Faraz qilaylik bu tenglama λ_1 va λ_2 ildizlarga ega bo'lsin. Quyidagi hollarni qaraymiz:

- $\lambda_1 \neq \lambda_2 \in \square$,
- $\lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda \in \square$,
- $\lambda_1 \neq \lambda_2 \in \square$.

Dastlab a) holni qaraylik. Bu holda (4) tenglama ushbu

$$(5) \quad D_{mt}^\alpha [x(t) + \lambda_i y(t)] = (a + \lambda_i c) [I_{mt}^\gamma x(t) + \lambda_i I_{mt}^\gamma y(t)] + f_1(t) + \lambda_i f_2(t), \quad i=1,2$$

ko'rinishdagi $x(t) + \lambda_i y(t)$ noma'lumlarga nisbatan chiziqli ikkita tenglama ko'rinishini oladi. Soddalik maqsadida quyidagi belgilashlarni kiritaylik:

$$(6) \quad x(t) + \lambda_i y(t) = z(t), \quad f_1(t) + \lambda_i f_2(t) = f_{3,i}(t), \quad a + \lambda_i c = \tilde{\lambda}_i, \quad i=1,2.$$

U holda (5) tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$(7) \quad D_{mt}^\alpha z(t) = \tilde{\lambda}_i I_{mt}^\gamma z(t) + f_{3,i}(t), \quad i=1,2.$$

Ushbu

$$(8) \quad I_{mt}^\alpha D_{mt}^\alpha \varphi(t) = \varphi(t) - (t-m)^{\alpha-1} \Gamma^{-1}(\alpha) I_{mt}^{1-\alpha} \varphi(t) \Big|_{t=m}$$

formulani e'tiborga olgan holda (7) tenglikning har ikki tomoniga I_{mt}^α operatorni tatbiq qilamiz. (2) shartlarni va kasr-tartibli integral operator yoyilmasini e'tiborga olsak, $z(t)$ noma'lum funksiyaga nisbatan

$$(9) \quad z(t) - \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t \frac{(t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha+\gamma)} z(\eta) d\eta = f_{4,i}(t)$$

ko'rinishdagi 2-tur Volterra integral tenglamasiga ega bo'lamiz. Bu yerda

$$(10) \quad f_{4,i}(t) = I_{mt}^\alpha f_{3,i}(t) + (t-m)^{\alpha-1} \Gamma^{-1}(\alpha) I_{mt}^{1-\alpha} z(t) \Big|_{t=m}.$$

U holda (9) tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishga keladi:

$$(11) \quad z(t) - \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,\eta) z(\eta) d\eta = f_{4,i}(t).$$

Oxirgi tenglama yechimini kema-ket yaqinlashish usulidan foydalanib topamiz. Nolinchi yaqinlashish sifatida $f_{4,i}(t)$ ni qabul qilamiz:

$$z_0(t) = f_{4,i}(t).$$

Birinchi va ikkinchi yaqinlashishlarni mos holda quyidagi formulalar orqali aniqlaymiz:

$$z_1(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,\eta) f_{4,i}(\eta) d\eta,$$

$$z_2(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,\tau) \left[f_{4,i}(\tau) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^\tau K(\tau,\eta) f_{4,i}(\eta) d\eta \right] d\tau =$$

$$= f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t K(t,\eta) f_{4,i}(\eta) d\eta + \tilde{\lambda}_i^2 \int_m^t K_2(t,\eta) f_{4,i}(\eta) d\eta.$$

n-yaqinlashishni esa

$$z_n = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t \sum_{j=0}^n \tilde{\lambda}_i^j K_j(t,\eta) f_{4,i}(\eta) d\eta$$

formuladan foydalanib topamiz, bu yerda $K_j(t,\eta)$ - iteratsiyalangan yadrolar bo'lib,

$$K_1(t,\eta) = K(t,\eta) = (t-s)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} \Gamma^{-1}(\alpha+\gamma),$$

$$K_j(t,\eta) = \int_{\eta}^t K(t,\tau) K_{j-1}(\tau,\eta) d\tau. \quad j=2,3,\dots$$

Dastlab, $K_2(t,\eta)$ ni hisoblaylik:

$$K_2(t,\eta) = \int_{\eta}^t K(t,\tau) K(\tau,\eta) d\tau = \int_{\eta}^t \frac{(t-\tau)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} (\tau-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1}}{\Gamma^2(\alpha+\gamma)} d\tau. \quad j=2,3,\dots$$

Ushbu almashtirishni bajaramiz: $\tau = (t-\eta)s + \eta$. U holda beta va gamma-funksiya xossaligidan foydalansak [2],

$$\begin{aligned} K_2(t,\eta) &= \int_0^1 \frac{(t-\eta)^{2(\alpha+\gamma)-1} (1-s)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} s^{\alpha+\gamma-1}}{\Gamma^2(\alpha+\gamma)} ds = \frac{(t-\eta)^{2(\alpha+\gamma)-1}}{\Gamma^2(\alpha+\gamma)} \int_0^1 s^{\alpha+\gamma-1} (1-s)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} ds = \\ &= \frac{(t-\eta)^{2(\alpha+\gamma)-1}}{\Gamma^2(\alpha+\gamma)} B(\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma) = \frac{(t-\eta)^{2(\alpha+\gamma)-1} \Gamma^2(\alpha+\gamma)}{\Gamma^2(\alpha+\gamma) \Gamma[2(\alpha+\gamma)]} = \frac{(t-\eta)^{2(\alpha+\gamma)-1}}{\Gamma[2(\alpha+\gamma)]}. \end{aligned}$$

Matematik induksiya usulidan ko'rsatish mumkinki, $K_j(t,\eta)$ uchun quyidagi tenglik o'rinli:

$$K_j(t,\eta) = \frac{(t-\eta)^{j(\alpha+\gamma)-1}}{\Gamma[j(\alpha+\gamma)]}, \quad j=1,2,3,\dots$$

Endi $R(t,\eta; \tilde{\lambda}_i)$ rezolventani tuzamiz:

$$R(t,\eta; \tilde{\lambda}_i) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \tilde{\lambda}_i^{j-1} K_j(t,\eta) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_i^{j-1} (t-\eta)^{j(\alpha+\gamma)-1}}{\Gamma[j(\alpha+\gamma)]} = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_i^j (t-\eta)^{j(\alpha+\gamma)+\alpha+\gamma-1}}{\Gamma[j(\alpha+\gamma)+\alpha+\gamma]}.$$

$E_{\alpha,\beta}(z)$ - Mittag-Leffler funksiyasining yoyilmasidan foydalansak [3], rezolventani quyidagicha yozishimiz mumkin:

$$R(t,\eta; \tilde{\lambda}_i) = (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma,\alpha+\gamma}[\tilde{\lambda}_i (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma}].$$

U holda 2-tur Volterra integral tenglamalari nazariyasiga [4] asosan, (11) tenglama yechimi ushbu formula orqali aniqlanadi:

$$(12) \quad z(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[\tilde{\lambda}_i (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_{4,i}(\eta) d\eta.$$

Endi (6) va (12) tengliklarga asosan quyidagi tenglamalar sistemasini tuzamiz:

$$(13) \quad x(t) + \lambda_i y(t) = f_{4,i}(t) + \tilde{\lambda}_i \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[\tilde{\lambda}_i (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_{4,i}(\eta) d\eta, \quad i=1,2.$$

Oxirgi tenglamalar sistemasini algebraik qo'shish usulidan foydalanib, $x(t)$ va $y(t)$ noma'lum funksiyalarni

$$x(t) = f_{4,1}(t) + (a + \lambda_1 c) \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[(a + \lambda_1 c)(t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_{4,1}(\eta) d\eta - \lambda_1 y(t),$$

$$y(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda_1 - \lambda_2} \left\{ f_{4,1}(t) - f_{4,2}(t) + (a + \lambda_1 c) \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[(a + \lambda_1 c)(t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_{4,1}(\eta) d\eta - (a + \lambda_2 c) \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[(a + \lambda_2 c)(t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_{4,2}(\eta) d\eta \right\}$$

ko'rinishda bir qiymatli aniqlashimiz mumkin.

b) holni qaraylik. Bu holda (13) tenglamalar sistemasida quyidagi ikki noma'lumli bitta chiziqli differensial tenglamaga ega bo'lamiz:

$$x(t) + \lambda y(t) = f_4(t) + \tilde{\lambda} \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[\tilde{\lambda} (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_4(\eta) d\eta.$$

Oxirgidan $y(t)$ noma'lum funksiyani

$$y(t) = \frac{1}{\lambda} \left[f_4(t) + \tilde{\lambda} \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[\tilde{\lambda} (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_4(\eta) d\eta \right] - \frac{x}{\lambda}$$

ko'rinishda topamiz. So'ngra topilgan $y(t)$ funksiyani (1) tenglamalar sistemaning birinchi tenglamasiga qo'yib

$$(14) \quad D_{mt}^\alpha x(t) = \left(a - \frac{b}{\lambda} \right) I_{mt}^\gamma x(t) + \frac{b}{\lambda} I_{mt}^\gamma \left[f_4(t) + \tilde{\lambda} \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[\tilde{\lambda} (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_4(\eta) d\eta \right] + f_1(t)$$

tenglamani topamiz. Soddalik maqsadida

$$f_5(t) = \frac{b}{\lambda} I_{mt}^\gamma \left[f_4(t) + \tilde{\lambda} \int_m^t (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1} E_{\alpha+\gamma, \alpha+\gamma} \left[\tilde{\lambda} (t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma} \right] f_4(\eta) d\eta \right] + f_1(t),$$

$$(15) \quad \lambda' = a - b\lambda^{-1}.$$

belgilashlarni kiritganimizdan so'ng, (14) tenglama quyidagi ko'rinishni oladi:

$$D_{mt}^\alpha x(t) = \lambda' I_{mt}^\gamma x(t) + f_5(t).$$

Oxirgi tenglamaning har ikki tarafiga (8) formulani qo'llaymiz. Natijada quyidagi

$$(16) \quad x(t) - \lambda' \int_m^t \frac{(t-\eta)^{\alpha+\gamma-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha+\gamma)} x(\eta) d\eta = f_6(t)$$

ko'rinishdagi 2-tur Volterra integral tenglamasiga ega bo'lamiz. Bu yerda

$$(17) \quad f_6(t) = \frac{(t-m)^{\alpha-1}}{\Gamma(\alpha)} I_{mt}^{1-\alpha} x(t) \Big|_{t=m} + I_{mt}^\alpha f_5(t).$$

(16) tenglamaning yechimi (9) tenglamaning yechimi kabi topiladi.

Endi c) holni qaraylik. Bu holda {(1),(2)} Koshi masalasining yechimi a) holdagi kabi aniqlanadi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

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